

The Condensation of Ethyl Acetosuccinate with Phenols.

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The condensation of acetoacetic esters and their alkyl derivatives with phenols has been the subject of numerous investigations (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 929, 1646, 2187; 1899, 32, 3681; 1901, 34, 381, 423; Biginelli, *Gazzetta*, 1895, 24, ii, 492; Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2016; Jacobson and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 424; Dey, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 1606). The corresponding condensation of acetosuccinic esters with phenols does not, however, appear to have been studied hitherto. In the present paper, it is shown that ethyl acetosuccinate readily enters into condensation with a variety of phenols under the customary experimental condition with the production of α -pyrone derivatives. Thus α -naphthol condenses with ethyl acetosuccinate with the formation of ethyl-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone-3-acetate. The reaction taking place according to the following scheme:—

The constitution of the foregoing α -pyrone derivative follows from the fact that on hydrolysis it readily furnishes the corresponding monobasic acid, which when heated above its melting point is quantitatively transformed into 3:4-dimethyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone with the elimination of carbon dioxide. As the latter substance does not appear to have been described in the literature (*cf.* Dey,

Note: While the present paper was going through the press my attention was drawn to a short note published by Y. Sankaranarayanan and A. V. Lakshminarayan in the Proceedings of the Indian Science Congress, 1931, along similar lines; I undertook the work in January, 1930 and in fact the paper was written up for publication before the work of these authors was communicated. I therefore take the opportunity to place on record such results as I have obtained quite independent of these authors and leave further extension of this work to them.

loc. cit., 1608) its identity, was definitely established by the following synthesis :

Ethyl acetosuccinate similarly condenses with resorcinol with the formation of α -pyrones, of which a number of characteristic derivatives have been prepared.

The coumarin-3-acetic esters described in this paper do not react with aromatic *o*-hydroxy aldehydes according to Knoevenagel's method. This is somewhat surprising in view of the fact, that these aldehydes condense with the corresponding coumarin-4-acetic esters, under the above conditions with remarkable ease (*cf.* Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 107). Condensation of the coumarin-3-acetic acids with hydroxyaldehydes can, however, be brought about according to Perkin's method. Thus the sodium salt of 4-methylcoumarin-1:2- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetic acid readily condenses with salicylaldehyde with the production of 4-methyl-3-(3'-coumaryl)-1:2- α -naphthopyrone as follows :

The greater reactivity of the methylene group in coumarin 4-acetic acids compared to the same grouping in the derivatives of coumarin-3-acetic acids described above, can, in the opinion of the present author, be satisfactorily explained on the basis of the principle of induced alternate polarities as developed by Lapworth (*Mem. Manchester Phil. Soc.*, 1920, **64**, iii, 1; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 416), and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **109**, 1030, 1038; 1917, **111**, 959; also *Mem. Manchester Phil. Soc.*, 1920, **64**, (4), 17; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 427). The fundamental circumstance is this:—The double-linking between the carbon atoms 3 and 4 in coumarin and its derivatives is highly reactive and as such takes up the elements of bromine (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1871, **24**, 37), hydrocyanic acid (Bredt and Kallen, *Annalen*, 1896, **293**, 338), sodium bisulphite (Dey and Row, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 554), cyanoacetamide (Sheshadri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 166), etc., with the greatest facility. This unsaturated centre induces alternate polarity effects in the molecule, which in the cases of the coumarin-4- and -3-acetic acids can be best represented thus:

It follows therefore, that the coumarin-4-acetic acids would be relatively more reactive than the 3-acetic acids, so far as the behaviour of *o*-hydroxyaromatic aldehydes towards these substances is concerned.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of ethyl acetosuccinate.—In preparing considerable quantities of ethyl acetosuccinate required for this research, the

following modification of Ruheman's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 71, 330) was found to be convenient. Finely divided sodium (11.5 g.) was kept under benzene (200 c.c.) and gradually mixed with ethyl acetoacetate (65 g.) diluted with benzene (50 c.c.) the flask being cooled in ice-water during the operation. The sodio-derivative, which separated on keeping overnight, was then mixed with chloroacetic ester (62 g.) and the whole heated to boiling on the water-bath for two hours. The product was then cooled, mixed with water and the benzene layer separated, washed with water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue of ethyl acetosuccinate on distillation under reduced pressure boiled at 150°/25 mm. (yield, 62 g.).

Condensation of ethyl acetosuccinate with α -naphthol: Formation of ethyl 4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone-3-acetate.—A mixture of α -naphthol (14 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (21g.) was cooled in ice and slowly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (75 c.c.), the flask being vigorously shaken after each addition. The clear reddish-brown liquid, after remaining overnight, was then poured into excess of ice-water and the precipitated solid collected and thoroughly washed with cold water, after three crystallisations from dilute alcohol, the product was obtained in colourless silky needles, m.p. 137°, yield, 7g. (Found: C, 72.49; H, 5.49. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.97; H, 5.40 per cent.).

Hydrolysis and formation of 4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid.—The foregoing ester (5 g.) was heated under reflux with 10 p. c. alcoholic potash (25 c.c.) for 2 hours on the water-bath. The alcohol was distilled off, the residue dissolved in water cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The crude product after several crystallisations from acetic acid formed shining leaflets, m.p. 258°. (Found: C, 71.15; H, 4.64. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47 per cent.).

The *silver salt* was prepared in the usual way, as a white crystalline precipitate. (Found: Ag, 28.4. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4Ag$ requires Ag, 28.8 per cent.). On melting the above acid in a test tube, until the evolution of carbon dioxide ceases, 3:4-dimethyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone is obtained in almost quantitative yield. On crystallisation from acetic acid, it melts at 199°. (Found: C, 79.95; H, 5.65. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80.35; H, 5.35 per cent.).

Condensation of α -naphthol with ethyl methylacetoacetate.—The condensation was brought about according to Pechmann's method;

The product separated from acetic acid in long white needles, m.p. 199° and found to be identical with the product described above by analysis. (Found: C, 79.99; H, 5.52 per cent.) and by mixed m.p. 199°.

Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate.—Resorcinol (11 g.) was condensed with ethyl acetosuccinate (22 g.) in presence of 60 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid in the usual way. The product separated from a mixture of acetone and alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 162°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 63.69; H, 5.8. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.34 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared with acetyl chloride in presence of pyridine. It separated from dilute alcohol in fine leaflets, m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 62.92; H, 5.43. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 63.15; H, 5.26 per cent.).

The *benzoyl* derivative was prepared by the Schotten-Baumann method in pyridine solution. It crystallised from alcohol in fine plates, m.p. 127°. (Found: C, 69.23; H, 5.23. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.92 per cent.).

The *methyl ether* was prepared by shaking the solution of the coumarin in sodium hydroxide with rather more than the calculated quantity of methyl sulphate. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 78°. (Found: C, 65.85; H, 5.71. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.22; H, 5.80 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the above ester with alcoholic potash. It crystallises from 20 p. c. alcohol in slender needles, m.p. 268°. (Found: C, 61.13; H, 4.34. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.27 per cent.). The *silver salt* separated as a white precipitate. (Found: Ag 31.41. $C_{12}H_9O_5$ Ag, requires Ag, 31.67 per cent.).

The *anilide* of 4-methyl- α -naphthopyrone-3, acetic acid was prepared by boiling the acid (1.5 g) with aniline (5 c. c.) for 1 hour. The solid product was repeatedly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and alcohol. It crystallises from acetic acid in silky needles, m. p. 285°. (Found: N, 3.62. $C_{22}H_{17}NO_3$ requires N, 4.08 per cent.). It is very sparingly soluble in most organic solvents.

1:2- α -Naphthopyrone.—The sodium salt of 4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetic acid (10 g.), salicylaldehyde (7 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 g.) were mixed with a trace of iodine and heated on the oil-bath at 120° for 3-4 hours and then at 180° for 2 hours. The

product thus obtained was then digested with water and filtered. It was purified from pyridine (using animal charcoal) and formed colourless crystals, m. p. 311°. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 4.05. $C_{23}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 77.9; H, 3.9 per cent.). It is sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents but dissolves freely in pyridine and nitrobenzene.

All attempts to condense ethyl-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetate with salicylaldehyde in presence of piperidine (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 113) were unsuccessful.

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